

Design of a 150kW transformer with integrated series inductance for future aerospace applications by using artificial NN

Alberto Delgado, Andrés Ferrer and Miroslav Vasic

Abstract

The future of transportation hinges on the electrification of all vehicles. This article presents a novel design methodology for high power transformers in DC-DC converters dedicated to propulsion, specifically targeting voltage levels between 600 and 1.2 kV for next generation regional electric aircraft. Utilizing an artificial neural network (ANN), we establish an initial design benchmark for general specifications. Subsequently, we refined this design based on detailed specifications and established design rules, achieving a transformer with integrated series inductance of 20 kW/L integrating the liquid cooling. This work paves the way for more efficient and powerful electric propulsion systems in aviation.

Artificial Neural Network Construction

Analytical Equations

Geometry Conditions

Square voltage waveforms:

$$BA = \frac{\int V_p dt}{N_p} \rightarrow A = \frac{V_p}{f_{sw} N_p} \rightarrow A = C^2 \rightarrow C = \sqrt{\frac{V_p}{4f_{sw} B_{sat} N_p}}$$

$$P_{core} = \text{SteinmetzModified}(B)$$

Square Litz-wire:

$$A_{cu} = \frac{1}{j} \rightarrow A_{cu} k_{LW} = A_{bd} \rightarrow \phi_{bd} = \sqrt{A_{cu} k_{LW}}$$

- $W = (N_{winding} + 1)\delta + \phi_{bd} N_{winding}$
- $H = 2\delta + \phi_{bd} N_{turns}$
- $HW = A_{bd} k_{wd} N_{turns} N_{winding}$
- $l_{eff_{core}} = 2\left(H + \frac{C}{2}\right) + 2\left(W + \frac{C}{2}\right)$
- $HW \in \left[0.25 \frac{C}{2} l_{eff_{core}}, 0.5 \frac{C}{2} l_{eff_{core}}\right]$
- $H \in [W, 4W]$
- $Gap \in [0.001 l_{eff_{core}}, 0.01 l_{eff_{core}}]$

Design Guidelines for the Electromagnetic Optimization

Once the neural network is trained, an iteration of cases is performed based on the final specifications. This results in a design space based on losses and temperature. Also meeting the magnetizing and leakage inductances within a certain percentage. To do so, two steps are followed:

Manufacturing guides

Winding interleaving is used to achieve the desired leakage inductance. The strategy keeps the field generated by the primary winding connection and secondary winding orthogonal.

Experimental Results

Small-signal

$$L = \begin{pmatrix} 34,2 \mu H & 22,74 \mu H \\ 22,74 \mu H & 16,8 \mu H \end{pmatrix}$$

$$k = 94.89\%$$

$$L_{mag} = 30.8 \mu H$$

$$L_{lk} = 3.4 \mu H$$

Open Circuit test

Short Circuit test

New Prototype

Inductance Adjustment

Winding Optimization

$$\sigma_{litz} = \frac{N_{strands}}{2A_{bundle} F_s(\gamma) R_{DC}}$$

$$\mu''_{litz} = \frac{2N_{strands} G_p(\gamma)}{\sigma \omega \mu_0 A_{bundle}}$$

Since σ is equal, the skin effect is the same for all. However, we optimize the proximity effect by reducing μ'' .